

The Municipalities in Transition System

Version 1.5

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“Sustainable development is more about the organisation of processes than about particular outcomes. It is about the modes of problem treatment and the types of strategies that are applied to search for solutions and bring about more robust paths of social and technological development”

(Voß & Kemp, 2006)

1. What is the Municipalities in Transition System?

The Municipalities in Transition System (MiTS)¹ provides a local Community a way to reorganize itself towards sustainability and wellbeing, responding to the great challenges² of this historical period, adopting systemic thinking³ and a specific set of methodologies, tools and principles.

1.1 - Who is the MiT System for?

The MiT System is designed to foster the process of transformative collaborations within the Community. An ideal implementation would see all the key Actors of the Community aware of the availability of the System and able to benefit from its use directly or indirectly.

During the design of the MiTS we considered three main starting point scenarios:

1. Process generated and led by the local government
2. Process generated and led by one or more Actors in civil society
3. Process generated and led by both together

Our intent is to provide a system applicable to all these scenarios.

1.2 - Features of the system

Here is a list of features we considered fundamental for a system of this kind:

1. It has a Purpose (see also 2.1 and 2.2)
2. It's closely linked to the Transition principles (see also 2.1)
3. It's implementable in a top-down and/or a bottom-up approach
4. It's powerful enough to cope with high levels of complexity and uncertainty
5. It's simple enough to be relatively easy to learn and to use in real life
6. It has a low level of preconditions for adoption (low resources, low technology)

¹ In the beta version we called it "framework" which remains an accurate term, but which turned out to be difficult to understand and translate. We have therefore opted for the use of the term "system".

² Climate Change ([IPCC - AR5](#) and [IPCC - AR6 Synthesis](#)), scarcity of resources, loss of biodiversity, pollution, increase in inequalities ... ([Planetary Boundaries](#))

³ For a primer on systemic thinking you can check the videos of the [System Thinking Course](#) of the Complexity Lab or refer to [Thinking in Systems: a Primer](#) by Donella Meadows.

7. It's easily adaptable to a wide variety of very different contexts and cultures
8. It's designed to be iteratively evolved through its use
9. It fosters a model of shared/diffused governance
10. It's capable of improving the quality of the cooperation between the involved Actors
11. It's preparatory to a Deep Adaptation⁴ community strategy
12. It works

2. Some fundamental premises

We are fully aware that reading this document and entering the use of MiTS will produce two apparently contradictory effects:

1. Feeling that what is described is already something you know very well and do normally.
2. Feeling that what is described is out of focus, vague and difficult to understand.

Often the two feelings emerge from the same item. Consider this effect as normal in the first phase, please don't worry and take it as it is. This is typical when you start moving into systemic thinking, and every change of the work culture feels strange to start with. Things will become very clear when we move on to the practical phases of using MiTS and the effects on real life are observed.

The system has been designed and shaped according to the following principles, which we now summarize here very briefly.

2.1 About Transition principles

The Head-Heart-Hands (HHH) principles⁵ at the core of the Transition Movement proved to be effective and disruptive in many different situations and socio-economic contexts. They were a central inspiration in the development of the MiTS:

Head: act on the basis of the best information and evidence available and apply collective intelligence to find better ways of living, keeping a strong systemic vision.

Heart: work with compassion, valuing and paying attention to the emotional, psychological, relational and social aspects of the ongoing work.

Hands: turn our vision and ideas into a tangible reality, initiating practical projects and starting to build a new, healthy economy in the place you live.

For a better understanding of the statements above it can also be useful to broaden the way in which we define and express the same ideas through a set of goals to achieve:

⁴ Concept inspired by Jem Bendell's homonymous paper, intended here as ready to help the community develop elements of resilience in a worst case scenario (<http://www.lifeworth.com/deepadaptation.pdf>).

⁵ <https://transitionnetwork.org/about-the-movement/what-is-transition/principles-2/> ; you can also check the Database entry on [HHH](#).

Respect resource limits and create resilience – The urgent need to eliminate greenhouse gas emissions, quickly phase out our reliance on fossil fuels and make wise use of precious resources is at the forefront of everything we do. Our aim is to build resilient communities that can adapt to external socio-ecological shocks as climate change or economic instability.

Promote inclusivity and social justice – The most disadvantaged and powerless people in our societies are likely to be most affected by rising fuel and food prices, resource shortages and extreme weather events. We need to increase the chances of all groups in society to live well, healthily and with sustainable livelihoods.

Adopt subsidiarity (self-organisation and decision making at the appropriate level) – The intention of the Transition model is not to centralise or control decision making, but rather to work with everyone so that it is practiced at the most appropriate, practical and empowering level.

Pay attention to balance – In responding to urgent, global challenges, individuals and organizations can end up feeling stressed, closed or constrained rather than open, connected and creative. We create space for reflection, celebration and rest to compensate for the moments when we're busy getting things done. We explore different ways of working which engage our heads, hands and hearts and enable us to develop collaborative and trusting relationships.

Be part of an experimental, learning network – Transition is a real-life, real-time global social experiment. Being part of a network means we can create change more quickly and more effectively, drawing on each other's experiences and insights. We want to acknowledge and learn from failure as well as success – if we're going to be bold and find new ways of living and working, we won't always get it right on the first attempt. We will be open about our processes and will actively seek and respond positively to feedback.

Freely share ideas and power – Transition is a grassroots movement, where ideas can be taken up rapidly, widely and effectively because each community takes ownership of the process itself. Transition looks different in different places and we want to encourage rather than unhelpfully constrain that diversity.

Collaborate and look for synergies – The Transition approach is to work together as a community, unleashing our collective genius to obtain a greater impact together than we can as individuals. We will look for opportunities to build creative and powerful partnerships across and beyond the Transition movement and develop a collaborative culture, finding links between projects, creating open decision-making processes and designing events and activities that help people make connections.

Foster positive visioning and creativity – Our primary focus is not on being against things, but on developing and promoting positive possibilities. We believe in using creative ways to engage and involve people, encouraging them to imagine the future they want to inhabit. The generation of new stories is central to this visioning work, as is having fun and celebrating success.

2.2 - The MiTS Purpose

This list of goals above is probably also the best way to explain what the use of the MiTS is trying to produce in a community that adopts it: what we could call the MiTS Purpose.

“To create deep cultural and practical changes towards sustainability and wellbeing through the implementation of the Transition Principles”

2.3 - Resilience principles

Another concept that is central for Transition processes and ideas is resilience, and many of the indications, methodologies, tools we are proposing are designed to contribute towards resilience at several levels⁶.

2.4 - Theory of fluxes

As far as we know this is not something already defined at the academic level⁷. It derives mainly from empirical work on the field with municipalities and communities, as well as marketing theories, and it was partially inspired by the work of the economist [David Lane](#)⁸ on complexity and social interactions.

The point is that we often try to produce change and new cultural assets by creating “groups”. One of the typical definitions in classical sociology can be the following:

A group in sociology exhibits cohesiveness to a larger degree. Aspects that members in the group may share include: interests, values, ethnic/linguistic background, roles and kinship. One way of determining if a collection of people can be considered a group is if individuals who belong to that collection use the self-referent pronoun "we;" using "we" to refer to a collection of people often implies that the collection thinks of itself as a group.

However when we organize ourselves in groups we automatically set some conditions that are inherent to groups that allow certain dynamics and forbid others.

⁶ A useful reference is the “Principles for Building Resilience Sustaining Ecosystem Services in Social-Ecological Systems” - Biggs, R. M. Schlüter - ISBN: 9781107082656 - [Link](#)

⁷ A further exploration of this subject is certainly necessary, Particularly in the field of [social innovation theories](#).

⁸ David A. Lane - Complexity and Innovation Dynamics; Envisioning a Socially Sustainable Future.

Some of the conditions that we see in groups and we considered particularly interesting for our project purpose are the following:

GROUPS	
Common analysis	A group normally needs to have a common/similar analysis of reality.
Common vision and goals	A group normally needs to have common/similar general vision and goals.
We are similar, we are WE	A group normally develops an identity and borders/edges. In a group we define who is in and who is out.
Direct relations	A group operates in direct relationship within its membership (in person or virtually).
Time and space unity	A group normally acts within a definite space and time, it needs some synchronicity in the way it operates.
Common projects	A group normally develops common projects.

Table 1

Observing these characteristics it is easy to understand that groups are not particularly suitable to foster a **transversal** change, like the one we need, in order to produce sustainability for human societies. For this reason we developed the concept of **fluxes**: social dynamics with the characteristic to move and influence wider portions of society in a transversal way.

To better understand this concept we can think of what the marketing system does to promote, for instance, a technology like the “smart phone”. The system sends a signal to everyone to convince them that a smartphone is something they need/want. This signal works as a flux hitting simultaneously different targets at different levels (the top manager and the unemployed, the young person and the old one). However the final product (the smartphone) will be sold focusing on “groups” (targeting the customers): smartphones for rich people, for geeks, very cheap models (“even you can have one!”), and so on. The point is that if you want to sell that product to *everyone* you need first a “flux” informing, connecting and fostering as many groups as possible at the same time.

By analogy, if you’d like to produce systemic change, a wide social evolution, you should probably generate, promote, support and take care of the right fluxes or you’ll end up involving only certain niches of the system (the risk is *preaching to the converted* only).

If we compare the characteristics of fluxes with those of groups we can note some interesting differences:

GROUPS	FLUXES ⁹
Common analysis and need	Common analysis and need
Common vision and goals	No need for common vision and goals
We are similar, we are WE	No need to be WE
Direct relations	No need for direct relations
Time and space unity	No need for time and space unity
Common projects	No need for common projects

Table 2

With fluxes we can do things that can't be done with groups, like making people with different views produce positive effects in a community without fighting each other, or without having to connect between them. This can prove quite life-changing for everyone active in social innovation processes.

All this to say that the MiTS design tries to incorporate the use and care of fluxes in its model (in addition and as a complement to the care of groups). More on this topic in the Annex 1 of this same document. You can also check the [Database entry](#) on this topic.

2.4 - Stochastic design

Another basic concept that guided the creation of MiTS concerns the need to face extreme complexity and resource scarcity for anyone trying to promote systemic change in our society.

One of the purposes of the MiTS is to help every actor to “design and plan” observing the opportunities arising around them, and spotting carefully when and where “energy” is available. Energy and opportunities can manifest themselves in many different forms, such as the availability of human and economic resources, the presence of physical space, equipment, skills, the availability of solutions to specific problems, etc.

Planning and implementing actions to promote sustainability and systemic change can be very difficult and ineffective. The world around us is constantly changing and a traditional, linear way to design and plan often proves ineffective. On certain occasions we might want to design a specific action, while not all the necessary conditions are in place to make it happen. This can lead to extreme tiredness, making us (and the community) consume a lot of time and resources, eventually getting a disproportion between the effort made and the results achieved, in many cases not reaching the expected goal.

Acting mainly on “opportunities” and “energy” availability (i.e. where the necessary conditions are present) makes things easier and increases the number of actions that can be performed with higher impacts on reality. We call this attitude “stochastic design” to stress the concept of having

⁹ It may be necessary, in the future, to agree on a different and more complete definition of the characteristics of the fluxes.

a constant attention to the random evolution of the environment, recognizing and accepting variables, and designing on that attitude but **without losing the scope of our work.**

The risk is in fact that following the opportunities, say for example money available through a government incentive campaign, we end up doing what the campaign is asking us to do, even if we don't really need it, or it is not aligned with our scope, but only because there are funds. This can be as ineffective and time consuming as the pursuit of unattainable goals. You can also check the [Database entry](#) on this topic.

By the way, there is no need for the users to learn much more about it, the concept is embedded in the whole system. Every suggested procedure is oriented towards this attitude.

Let's move on to the MiTS description.

Managers are not confronted with problems that are independent of each other, but with dynamic situations that consist of complex systems of changing problems that interact with each other. I call such situations messes. Problems are extracted from messes by analysis. Managers do not solve problems, they manage messes.

Russell L. Ackoff
(organizational theorist)

3. Basic structure of the MiTS

We begin now outlining the key elements of this system:

- | | |
|--|-------------------------------------|
| ● The Functions | <i>What does it allow me to do?</i> |
| ● The Governance Model | <i>How do we make decisions?</i> |
| ● The Grid | <i>Where are we going to play?</i> |
| ● The Pattern Language Database | <i>Where are the right tools?</i> |
| ● The Community of Practice | <i>Who supports me?</i> |

Warning!

All the following elements are designed to be eventually adapted to local contexts. However, we suggest you don't make adaptations while in the early phase of using the system (unless the need is absolutely clear and with an agreement with your Tutor). See more in the "MiTS adaptation" chapter 5 of this document.

3.1 - The Functions

The MiTS is designed to perform a set of functions that we consider extremely important for every community trying to evolve and change.

These are:

- 1. The Evaluation and Diagnosis Function** - A way for the community to easily evaluate its initiatives in an approximate way, but still sensible enough for the present purpose, and to set a reference Baseline from where its path toward the MiTS Purpose is starting. This will also let the same community to keep track of the progresses and changes over time. At the same time the MiTS helps to spot energy, resources and weak points of the community systems and actions, providing a diagnosis tool to inform other activities.
- 2. The Co-Design Function** - A better way to connect different actors and help them co-design plans and actions. The way the MiTS works tends to break walls and

compartments, making the power of connections, cooperation and sharing more visible and valuable.

3. **The Co-Implementation Function** - This is a consequence of the previous function. In a world facing various levels of scarcity, the need of doing a lot with less can be a key ability to pursue. By taking actions together, we are more likely to be able to support shifts in culture and behaviour and to achieve impacts which are more proportionate to the ecological and social crises we face. Adding the energy of different actors we produce subsidiarity and we use complementarity to the best.
4. **The ToolBox Function** - The MiTS aims to make readily available in its Pattern Language Database a variety of tools and concepts from around the world that are particularly suitable for the kind of process we are trying to foster. It will also suggest how to connect and use them in the most effective way, highlighting strengths, risks and weaknesses for each one of them.
5. **Cultural Leverage Function** - Using the MiTS will help people gravitate towards systemic thinking and key patterns towards sustainability. This will happen for those aware and in direct contact with the MiTS but also for those that will use the tools or that are part of processes designed within the MiTS logic. The basic principles will be replicated in a fractal way all over the system elements.
6. **The Governance Innovation Function** - The MiTS introduces an innovative and disruptive governance model within the start-up and implementation teams managing the system and beyond. This function is transversal to all the others.

3.2 - The governance model

Whatever process or project you want to implement within a community you are probably going to face all the dynamics that characterize our cultural systems: conflict, competition, distrust, misunderstanding, etc. That is how reality is most of the time: messy and difficult.

Since we are trying to put in place a different kind of dynamic within the community, we have equipped MiTS with a special model of Governance called Sociocracy 3.0¹⁰ (S3) to provide what follows:

1. Strong orientation to inclusiveness and enhancement of collective thinking
2. Strong orientation to cooperation and subsidiarity
3. High levels of transparency, effectiveness and accountability
4. Great flexibility and adaptability to a wide range of different situations
5. Capable of disrupting most of the negative dynamics of groups (consent based)
6. Simple linkability to MiTS (Transition) principles
7. Nestability with other traditional methodologies (required by laws or institutional processes)
8. An open source methodology

¹⁰ You can find all the information about this methodology originally developed in 2014 by James Priest and Bernhard Bockelbrink on <https://sociocracy30.org/>

S3 develops from a very smart combination of classic Sociocracy (a democratic methodology), Agile¹¹ (a set of values and principles created to develop better software) and Lean¹² (a management tool to create more value with less resources). It fits very effectively in the MiTS because most of the goals, principles and problems to be solved are the same, it is a real game-changer piece of the system.

To put a MiTS Pioneer in place in a community the minimum requirement is the constitution of a Local Startup Team (LST) formed by the representatives of the municipalities and at least two other Actors from civil society. This will then evolve in a larger Local Implementation Team (LIT).

The use of the S3 methodology is required for the management of these groups and considered an indispensable part of the MiTS.

3.3 - The grid

As we already pointed out, municipalities, activists and all the actors of a community have to face the complexity of their local system day by day. Like in a boardgame, the first element of the MiTS is designed to provide a clearer, more systemic view of the “playing field”.

The Grid performs three specific functions:

- Defines **Actors and Actions Categories**
- Shows **Relational Proximity** between the actors
- Act as an organizer of **Actions and Tools**

¹¹ [Agile manifesto](#)

¹² [Lean Enterprise Institute](#)

Below is the basic layout of the **Grid**.

		Actors Categories							
Actions Categories	U Upper Institutional Levels	A Municipality Political	B Municipality Organization	C Controlled Entities	D Suppliers	E Organizations	F Businesses	G Public	H Networks
1 Vision									
2 Organization									
3 Planning									
4 Technical aspects									
5 Relation									
6 Cultural change									
7 Networking									

Fig. 1

The Actors Categories

The upper horizontal row shows the key **Actors** categories organized in 9 columns. The way they are ordered suggests the relational distance between them.

This indication of distance must not be considered in a rigid way: reality can show us a great variety of situations. We highly encourage the use of the present column distribution, with some possible slight modifications, as discussed with the Tutor. You can see a different color for the first and the last column that indicates that those actors are out of the community domain and/or space.

Here is the list of the basic Actors Categories:

Actors Categories								
U. Upper Institutional Levels	A. Municipality Political	B. Municipality Organization	C. Controlled Entities	D. Suppliers	E. Organizations	F. Businesses	G. Public	H. Networks

Fig. 2

For example, considering the relational distance among categories as the distance between columns, the **Political** level of the municipality can interact more easily with the **Organization** level of the municipality than with the **Suppliers**. This gives a very quick way to roughly

estimate the amount of effort (energy, resources) one actor needs to reach and interact with another actor (particularly when the goal is to produce support, suggest changes, etc.).

The list below will help you to identify the **Actors** and focus on a few important traits they present:

- U. **UPPER INSTITUTIONAL LEVELS** Regional/National/International governments, authorities, etc.
They are out of the community domain and not directly influenced by the community but they can produce effects in the community with their actions and policies, receive feedback, be inspired, involved or indirectly influenced by actions/decisions of the community, etc.
- A. **MUNICIPALITY: Political level**
Elected (they care about votes and voters), they have to deal with political opponents and competitors, they often stay in charge only a few years, and are often forced to practice a “short-term thinking” attitude. They can be almost volunteers in small municipalities, and well paid and more powerful in many big cities.
- B. **MUNICIPALITY: Organization level**
Employees (civil servants) or freelancers often stay for a long time, very often have a deep understanding of the “municipality machine”, they are the practical “door to action”. They can easily be overwhelmed by the workload and suffer scarcity of resources.
- C. **CONTROLLED ENTITIES:** structures, consortia, companies directly controlled by the Municipality
Entities that are strongly connected to the municipality (public water services, waste management services, maintenance, social services), can be controlled in a very direct way, they have to act as the municipality wants.
- D. **SUPPLIERS:** public and private suppliers
Entities connected through stable or occasional economic contracts. These are suppliers of the municipality or of any other actor in the community.
- E. **ORGANIZATIONS:** non-profit, associations, schools, hospitals, universities, unions, parties, etc.
Non-profit organized entities that are present in the territory, e.g. organized activists.
- F. **BUSINESSES:**
Companies, cooperatives, freelancers, private schools and universities, business oriented organizations.
- G. **PUBLIC:** families, citizens, individuals, people
Taken as a single unity (one citizen, one family) or as not organized groups (all the people living in that street, an area...).
- H. **NETWORKS:** other municipalities, municipality consortia, other actors (far away in terms of relational distance), etc.

Entities that may or may not be present in the territory but that we know are important to consider to achieve a particular goal. National or international networks or NGOs, organizations out of the community domain not sitting on a higher institutional rank (ex. the Red Cross).

You may find Actors not so easy to classify, don't spend much time in finding "the perfect column" just place it in the most plausible position and be consistent if a similar case re-occurs.

Also consider that a particular entity can play different roles. A business company can appear in the column F (Businesses) when it's acting in complete operational freedom, but in the column D (Suppliers) when acting under the bond of a contract with another actor of the community. In MiTS we care a lot about interactions. For instance, if a local government wants to produce a change in the way a business operates, having a contract in place with that particular business makes things easier than if they only have moral suasion as a tool and no other links to the business.

The Actions Categories

The first vertical column on the left indicates the Actions categories we want to focus on in our "playing field". Again this is not to be taken with rigidity and we acknowledge that we can have overlaps.

Actions Categories
1. Vision
2. Organization
3. Planning
4. Technical aspects
5. Relations
6. Cult Change
7. Networking

Fig. 3

1. **VISION:** where do we want to go, what we see in the future
Actions and processes that tend to create/evolve/change a vision.
2. **ORGANIZATION:** people, roles, structures, governance, procedures, etc.

Actions and processes that tend to create or modify aspects about how the actors are organising/governing themselves or with others.

3. **PLANNING:** sector plans, policies integrations, budgets, etc.
Actions and processes that tend to create an action plan, step by step procedures.
4. **TECHNICAL ASPECTS:** monitoring, data, technicalities, laws and regulations, etc
Actions and processes that modify the state of the system through technology and technical aspects in general (also social technologies).
5. **RELATIONS:** within Actors, social aspects, caring aspects, etc.
Actions and processes that want to create, modify or improve relations between actors (key sentence: the way we talk to each other).
6. **CULTURAL CHANGE:** communication, training, involvement, empowerment, etc.
Actions and processes that tend to create, modify or improve the knowledge and the understanding of the “world”.
7. **NETWORKING:** networking, diversity, info exchange, comparison, etc.
Actions and processes that tend to create, modify or improve connections between actors (key sentence: the way we share and work together).

The cells

Obviously Actors and Actions intersect in cells that we are going to use as containers when we perform the functions of our System. We can also imagine the grid like a well organized cupboard where we can store everything we need for our “transition” activity with the community, and the cells as drawers. Each cell can be identified by the letter of its column and the number of its row; this will be very useful to connect the cells to the records of the MiTS Pattern Language Database as we will see in the next chapter.

Cells are mainly used to store a set of 3 values for each cell:

1. Observed impact/presence¹³ **(b)**
2. Potential or expected impact/presence **(p)**
3. Evaluated impact/presence **(e)**

To each we can assign a value ranging from -10 to 10 where positive values measure a positive impact or presence (therefore in support of the goals of the action and the MiTS purpose) and the negative values negative impact or presence (therefore impediments, problems, etc.).

¹³ What does “impact/presence” mean? We try to observe and report on the Grid who is doing the actions, who else is involved and affected, how important is the positive (or negative) impact the action is creating. The LIT will quickly develop an internal culture on how to interpret their community reality transforming it into consistent values on the Grid.

4 Technical aspects	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0
5 Relations	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0
6 Cultural change	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0
7 Networking	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0

Fig. 5

We know it might look scary and complex now, but using it will prove it to be much easier than you can imagine. To prove this, the first 6 pilot communities that used MiTS started with a much simpler version of this grid and, despite this, it looked frightening to them also, but in a very short time they were all asking to add all the elements you see now, to make the whole grid more powerful and useful.

3.4 - The Cynefin Space

Cynefin (pronunciation kə'nevɪn is a Welsh word meaning *habitat, haunt, acquainted, familiar*) is a conceptual framework created in 1999 by the management consultant Dave Snowden when he worked for IBM Global Services. It identifies 5 spaces in which to place what we observe around us. To each of these spaces then corresponds a specific sequence of action, which should increase the chances of success.

Fig. 6

In the MiTS context we suggest to use Cynefin as a quick, auxiliary method to Analyze and Plan our Actions. A very quick explanation on the use of this tool is going to be part of the training for the Local Implementation Team. Every action will be then marked by its position in the right Cynefin space and this will be useful to provide a set of first indications for its management (evaluation, development, improvement, modification, etc.)

3.5 - The Evaluation Cycles

Evaluation Cycles (ECs) are particularly helpful when we evaluate an action or we design a new one. We provide a number of basic ECs that we consider fundamental to guide our activity together with the use of the Grid, but the users could also decide to develop more cycles if they feel the need.

Each Evaluation Cycle is based on a simple set of three questions and for each one of them we ask to express a rating score from 0 to 10 where 0 is equivalent to a “full no” or “disagreement” and 10 is equivalent to a “full yes” or “full agreement”.

The HHH Cycle

The first cycle is a way to verify if the action we evaluate or plan fulfills Head/Heart/Hands (HHH) logic. This is the most important of the cycles and can't be skipped for any reason.

It can be performed in a very rapid way answering the following 3 questions:

1. Is this action based on the best available data? (Head step)
2. Is it considering and taking care of emotional/relational consequences for everyone involved? (Heart step)
3. Does it produce practical effects? (Hands step)

Or it can be used at different levels of complexity to fine tune its effectiveness. Here is a more complete way to see it:

1. Is this action based on the best available data? (Head step)
 - a. Would you classify the data as very solid and true¹⁴?
 - b. Would you classify the data as good but with some doubts?
 - c. Would you classify the data as quite uncertain?
2. Is it considering and taking care of emotional/relational consequences on everyone involved? (Heart step)
 - a. Is this producing fear or conflict?
 - b. Is this highlighting positivity, happiness, joy... ?
 - c. Is there “space” and “time” to take care for emotions?
 - d. Are participants feeling organically connected to the action¹⁵?

¹⁴ Official data are not always solid and true so are not enough to answer “yes”. This can be delicate, but connecting with reality is paradoxically a difficult task in the information era. You have to surf in a sea of fake news, reports on commission, low quality peer to peer papers, politically oriented pseudo scientific information, green washing, etc. The availability and the quality of the information can also be heavily influenced by the country you are operating in, the culture, the language, etc.

¹⁵ In the MiTS work environment empowerment or participation shouldn't be considered “good things” if not after analysing the context and the purpose of the action. Sometimes they are, sometimes not, our aim is facilitating each actor to find its right spot in the action development.

3. Does it produce practical effects? (Hands step)
 - a. Can this produce a useful change¹⁶?
 - b. Can the change last?
 - c. Can the change foster further useful changes?
 - d. Can you see useful changes in everyday's life of people?

The WWW Cycle

The WWW Cycle should always follow the first one as a safety reminder of the power of connections and inclusion. It is based on the following 3 very simple questions:

1. Who is there? (are the very fundamental/natural actors part of the actions?)
 - a. Ideally they should be involved in the governance of the action and given S3 objections right.
 - b. The minimum score of this question should always be 100.
2. Who is missing? (Are there other natural/well connecting actors that are not present?)
3. Who else should be there? (Are there other actors that might contribute to improve this action?)

We know that this cycle can be confusing, here is a practical example that can help you to better understand the 3 questions above:

WWW example

A Municipality has some money available to offer to the students of the local school a laboratory in Domestic Sustainable Waste Management. A local association has trainers already doing this type of activity in schools.

Who is there?

The fundamental actors here are: the Municipality (say the officer responsible for the project), the School (the teachers directly involved, the principal, the didactic direction, the students), the Association (the trainers).

Who is missing?

Other natural actors are: the families of the involved students, the other teachers in the school (those not directly involved in the laboratory activity), the Company/Service managing waste in the municipality that could help and provide info. All not essential but very connected and interesting to involve.

Who else should be there?

Other potential contributors: a similar school in the neighboring municipality (they might be interested in following this example), the shops selling the tools needed for the laboratory (they might offer the equipment), etc. All not essential and not so easy to engage but a way to amplify the effect of the action.

¹⁶ Change (or innovation) for the sake of change is not an intended outcome of the MiTS. We pursue changes useful to achieve the MiTS purpose.

The Flux Cycle

This cycle helps you to understand if the action, in addition to pursuing its specific objectives, is also producing or could potentially produce a beneficial flux effect on the community. This can be done asking this set of questions:

1. Is this action sowing transition memes¹⁷?
2. Is it connecting, supporting, complementing other actions?
3. Can it be supported by a range of different sectors of the community?

See the *Working With Fluxes* annex for a better understanding of this cycle.

The Deep Adaptation Value Cycle

This cycle is used to roughly estimate the value of the Action for the resilience of the community. Here are the set of questions to be asked:

1. How much impact has this action on basic services for the community (food, energy, shelter, relations/democracy).
2. How vital is this action for the services which it impacts?
3. What priority should the community put on the protection of this action in case of a disruptive event?

The Resilience Cycle

This cycle is used to evaluate the resilience of the action itself.

1. Does this action have a back-up protection of redundancy in the community?
2. At what level is this action resourced within the community?
3. How easily can the governance of this action be moved to another governance system in case of a disruptive event?

More Evaluation Cycles could be added if necessary in the future, or in the moment depending on the local conditions.

¹⁷ A meme is an idea, behavior, or style that spreads from person to person within a culture—often with the aim of conveying a particular phenomenon, theme, or meaning represented by the meme. A meme acts as a unit for carrying cultural ideas, symbols, or practices, that can be transmitted from one mind to another through writing, speech, gestures, rituals, or other imitable phenomena with a mimicked theme. Supporters of the concept regard memes as cultural analogues to genes in that they self-replicate, mutate, and respond to selective pressures. Example: “In nature the strongest survives” is a very simple meme on which to build an entire human cultural system or “A mosquito net can save lives” is a simple meme that has saved millions of lives around the world while “Smoking is cool” killed millions. For a reference Richard Dawkins “The selfish gene” (4th edition Oxford Landmark Science 2017) and Susan Blackmore “The Meme Machine” (Oxford University Press, 1999). Also Yuval Noah Harari “Sapiens” (Random House).

“The way to build a complex system that works is to build it from very simple systems that work.”

Kevin Kelly
(founder of *Wired* magazine)

3.6 - The Pattern Language Database

The second element of the MiTS is a database where we collect all the transition patterns that we already know and those that we will discover in the future. The Database is accessible to MiTS users through the web and it will probably be available also on paper in the future.

The word *patterns*¹⁸ is the most appropriate to describe the contents of the database, but it is also abstract and unusual for the most. From now on we will use the words *Actions* and *Tools* instead, choosing one or the other depending on the type of pattern we are referring to.

What are Tools in the database?

They can be a simple way to solve or handle a very specific problem:

Problem: Where do I get reliable information about new PV technology?

Tool: Subscribe to the *XYW* web newsletter!

Or more complex questions:

Problem: How can we evolve the vision of the municipality employees?

Tool: Awareness raising and team building training program and methodology.

Tool: Deep ecology training program and methodology.

Tool: U-Lab training program.

Tool: Guided tour of the National Climate Observatory Center.

...

Or an even larger approach:

Problem: How do we involve citizens in that area of town?

Tool 1: Transition Street projects (examples, methodologies,...)

Tool 2: REconomy projects (examples, methodologies,...)

Tool 3: CSA scheme.

Tool ...

How do we organize the Tools in the database?

¹⁸ Pattern: any form of correlation between the state of elements within a system. The way the elements correlate can be recognized and repeated. Normally we recognize a pattern as such because we've already seen that same kind of organization, correlation, sequence of events elsewhere.

The main features of the MiTS database are:

1. It is organized as a Pattern Language database¹⁹
2. Therefore database records are connected with other relevant database records and we could call them *patterns*, according to the original definition of the Pattern Language methodology
3. Database records are connected to grid cells (one or more)
4. The Database contains specific and transversal Tools
5. Tools in the Database are there to serve the purpose of MiTS
6. Each record is designed to solve a specific problem

The Pattern Language concept was created for city planning, but in general it is a very interesting way to organize information when you are trying to keep and foster a systemic view. The way it works is quite self-explanatory, there is basically no learning curve for those that have to use the database and virtually no limits in the expandability of the system.

Our Pattern Language is organized around a logic of process²⁰. Let's see how it works.

The database records (patterns)

Here is the general layout of every item of the MiTS database (more or less the same suggested by the original pattern language methodology):

The record template

Grid positions Tags Categories Trust ranking Languages	Title of the Tool/Action
	Up links (what we need to get ready to use/understand this Tool/Action)
	Description of the problem (that we are trying to solve)
	Short summary (what is this Tool/Action for?)
	Analysis of the problem and Tool description Analysis and tool description Risks and precautions Advantages Case study Tips for adaptation
	Solution (how this Tool/Action solves the problem)
	Down links (others patterns to check in this database to complement this Tool /Action or to follow after the present Tool/Action)

¹⁹ See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/A_Pattern_Language

²⁰ In the original you can see that the organization was around the scale of the area you wanted to plan on, from regions of a country to single rooms in a house.

Table. 3

Let's have a look at an example with some data inside (we are using fake links here simply to give you a general idea of how the item can look like). Refer to the Grid Template document when you need:

<p>ID: 00345</p> <p>Grid positions G.4</p>	<p>Neighborhood Draught Busters Group</p>
<p>Tags Energy Efficiency, Low Income, Homes, Volunteers, Insulation</p>	<p>Up links Check in advance: "Cheap insulation techniques" and "How to connect with your municipality for common actions". See also "How to run effective actions groups" and "Groups governance suggestions".</p>
<p>Categories G. Public</p>	<p>Description of the problem Buildings lose a great amount of energy through bad insulation and air leaks but in many cases complete renovations are not possible, particularly for people with low income. This means that millions of homes will never see the necessary actions to reduce energy needs.</p>
<p>Trust ranking ***</p>	<p>Short summary Draft Busters Groups are self organized groups of volunteers helping people in the neighborhood to improve houses insulation with simple and affordable techniques.</p>
<p>Languages: English Spanish</p>	<p>Analysis of the problem and Tool description</p> <p>The existing houses present in many communities are one of the major causes of energy consumption (around 40% in Europe), heating and cooling being the most impactful aspects for energy use and resulting emissions.</p> <p>Full retrofitting would be the best solution to take these houses at the best possible level of efficiency, but this is possible only when a lot of financial power is in place.</p> <p>To help those house owners and tenants without the possibility of resorting to complete retrofitting, volunteers local groups can be created under the name of "Draft Busters". They train themselves to do very easy insulation works DIY style and help others to spot and eliminate draft, insulate the attics, windows, hot water pipes, etc.</p> <p>The groups are organized [...]</p> <p>Sometimes creating a buying group to get the materials at a cheaper price and support local suppliers can be a nice consequence of this activity.</p> <p>Risks and precautions</p> <p>Check any legal aspects of offering this work in your country.. There are also practical risks (use of tools, damage to property and people, etc), so consider and arrange appropriate</p>

	<p>insurance coverage for the group [...]</p> <p>Personal Identification can be an issue, so it can be useful to coordinate well with local authorities and security forces to protect citizens from possible fraud. [...]</p> <p>Advantages</p> <p>This strategy can potentially reach citizens house by house, in the less affluent sections of the population. Can be also a good connection tool and a way to raise awareness on energy efficiency in general.</p> <p>Case study</p> <p>Particularly interesting is the experience of the DBG of the town of XXXXX. You can read about it following this link.</p>
	<p>Solution</p> <p>Form groups of volunteers to help people to do basic insulation actions in homes.</p>
	<p>Down links</p> <p>See also "Full energy efficiency retrofit plans" and "ESCO strategies" for a different approach to the same problem. Similar to this see also "Draft Busters Thermal Imager Tours" or "Draft Busters DIY Training".</p>

Table. 4

As you can see, the main body of the database record contains the most important information about the Tool and there is a number of fixed sections that are the same for each item. They should be quite self-explanatory and with use, this way of organizing information becomes quickly familiar.

Please note: The presence of the **Up Links** and **Down Links** is a particular feature. This is the way a Pattern Language database structure gently (or not so gently) pushes the user to keep a systemic view of the problems. It basically teaches this kind of attitude becoming an educational tool in itself. It suggests connections, prerequisites, consequences, possible further developments, alternatives and so on.

On the left column we collect a number of other very useful information:

Item

This is the identification number of the item.

ID:

Grid

It indicates the best position or positions in the grid where you can use this Tool. The first letter indicates the column, and the number the row (like in the battleship game). A Tool can have a very specific position or more than one.

Position

As already mentioned there are also Tools that are completely transversal, therefore they don't have a grid position indication and are collected in a separate category.

In the example above the "Neighborhood Draft Busters Group" item would be best used in the cell G.4.

Tags and Categories

These are indications to make the record searchable and easy to reach within a database that can become potentially very large.

Trust ranking

Social innovation and work on change, sustainability, etc. is about trial and error. Some of the Tools are well known, trialled and trustworthy, while others are new and trying to solve problems that no one has been able to solve before.

The "editorial staff" of the database will try to rank the records assigning a 0 to 5 stars indication following these general rules:

****** 4 or ***** 5 stars = High Trust**

Known for a long time and trialled with success. We are highly confident that the Tool/Action can solve the problem that presents.

**** 2 or 3 ***3 stars = Medium Trust**

Known for a long time and experimented but with a range of results. Not so old, good so far, be prudent.

*** 1 star = Low Trust**

Very new, promising but not enough data, be very prudent. Known, but with a range of results and very often failures, problems, etc.

Languages

Indicates the availability of translations of the record in other languages.

We might decide in future to add to this same area some other indications that can be useful for fast references, for instance something about the ease of implementation.

You show me a successful complex system, and I will show you a system that has evolved through trial and error.

Tim Harford

(economist)

3.7 - The Community of Practice (CoP)

So we have a set of principles, a Grid and a Database - what we need now are the users. The MiTS is designed to provide local administrators and civil society groups with a chance to connect and work together in a better way.

In our complex society and in the current complex times, this is a goal that cannot be achieved through something written on stones, the MiTS and everything around it need to be used and evolved by a live Community of Practice (CoP).

What we can imagine from now on is to have a local CoP in the municipalities where the framework will be in use, connected with a wider network of users at national and international level. Within the MiTS we are designing and implementing so far a community at international level²¹.

²¹ A specific document on CoP will be available soon.

Today the network of relationships linking the human race to itself and to the rest of the biosphere is so complex that all aspects affect all others to an extraordinary degree. Someone should be studying the whole system, however crudely that has to be done, because no gluing together of partial studies of a complex nonlinear system can give a good idea of the behavior of the whole.

Murray Gell-Mann

(physicist, Nobel laureate, father of the quark theory)

4 - Using the MiTS for the Pioneers

Can I use it in my community?

We suggest that you should become a Pioneer community assisted by a MiT Tutor, to successfully use the MiT System.

After a two years phase of development and testing in six pilot projects around the world (2017-2018), this is the first publicly available version of the MiT System. It's designed for a new run of two years called the "Pioneers Phase" where communities experimenting with it will be closely assisted by a tutor specialized in the use of the full MiTS for at least one year.

Having a tutor at your side is crucially important and we need time to train a team of people in charge of this role in different countries. MiTS wants to bring the activities of the community into a different space where real transformation is possible. On the other hand the current system is profoundly rooted in our cultures, and it prevents an evolution that takes into account a systemic view. Following the MiTS process could result in a very difficult task without the help of a tutor, leading practitioners to fall back into the old patterns and models.

Obviously, being now an open document with all the basic information and suggestions available, nobody is going to stop you from trying on your own (at your own risk).

4.1 - Trust our system

Facing complexity at the local level while simultaneously paying attention to the global scenario will prove difficult and messy even using the MiTS, so be ready for that. What we suggest is to trust the process and see what happens after a while.

At the beginning it can be strange and confusing, dealing with the complexity around us is quite an anxiogenic task, particularly if you really resist the temptation of trying to control it.

Our suggestion is: take it easy, follow the instructions and listen to your tutor, this system is designed to be inherently safe.

4.2 - Implementing MiTS in your community as a Pioneer

Starting point

As we stated before, the MiTS should be useful for processes driven by civil society organizations, local governments or both acting together, the last being the ideal condition.

Different starting conditions can bring different needs and strategies but in this phase of the MiTS we are selecting pioneers where we can have both together from the beginning.

Pioneers will be asked to:

1. Sign an agreement with Transition Network about this pioneering phase;
2. Create a Local Startup Team (LST) formed by the representatives of the municipalities and at least two other actors from civil society (ideally two actors from column E);
3. Implement the MiT System (ideally a two hours team meeting a week imagining one person for each organization involved);
4. Allocate a budget to support the activity at local level (mainly to cover the activity of the tutor).

In the following picture you can see the MiTS flow for the pioneers and in this chapter, you can have a quick overview of the required activities to implement the MiTS in your community.

Fig. 7

The MiTS local training and governance setting

The Local Implementation Team will receive training to learn more about the MiTS, its use and the pioneer management through the S3 governance methodology. The next phase will be activated when the group will have a sufficient mastery of the governance model.

Creating a Baseline

The first step in the use of the MiTS is the creation of a local baseline (or just baseline for short) through the analysis of 30 actions already in progress and that we imagine oriented to serve the purpose of MiTS.

It is a way to set a starting point, taking a picture of the state of the art of the municipality and its community. We are performing a first run of the **Evaluation and Diagnosis Function** of the System.

The idea is to use the MiTS grid to collect in an organized way every action we can spot ongoing around us. Examples of what we are looking for are: training on sustainable waste management, low emissions mobility plans, local food production schemes, information campaigns on energy efficiency, climate change adaptation training, circular and sharing economy activities, low impact mobility, community-making actions, social/minority inclusiveness initiatives etc.

We are trying to be easy, cheap, and effective. This system is designed by practitioners trying to make it as usable as possible and adaptable to very different starting point conditions. Therefore this collection of actions can be done in a very orderly and systematic way or through a more random process.

The pioneers will use a specific custom WordPress based platform to collect and process all the necessary info. The same platform can provide initial suggestions on the collected data.

The baseline in practice: collect data

The precise design of this activity will be defined by the LIT and carefully assisted by the tutor to end up with the set of the most important 30 actions that the community can spot. The scope of the Baseline is not to provide a precise, scientific measurement methodology but a way to more clearly see “the big picture” of the community. These are the steps you’ll follow:

1. Define, using S3, the best way to perform this activity in your context.
2. Start observing from what is obvious, plain and easy to spot (complexity will then emerge) and create a list of potential actions to be part of the baseline, then choose the most important 30.
5. Analyze and register each action on the MiTS WordPress platform. During the training we will play a lot with real life examples to make this task easier.

In the end you’ll be in the position to evaluate each single chosen action and the group of all actions together as a general overview. This is what we call *Baseline*.

There are other ways to proceed that you can explore on the Annex 2 - *Baseline Creation*.

The baseline in practice: baseline quantitative evaluation

Having now a Baseline, we can start a first quantitative evaluation of it. An ideal community wonderfully committed to change toward sustainability should produce a grid with every cell seeing many bold actions going on. Reality will probably bring different results.

In this phase only the first position (Observed impact/presence) of every cell will contain a value. The grid of a single action will therefore look similar to the following example:

SINGLE ACTION GRID:

		Actors Categories							
Actions Categories	U Upper Institutional Levels	A Municipality Political	B Municipality Organization	C Controlled Entities	D Suppliers	E Organizations	F Businesses	G Public	H Networks
	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e
1 Vision	0 0 0	2 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	-2 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	7 0 0	0 0 0
2 Organization	0 0 0	7 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0
3 Planning	0 0 0	4 0 0	5 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	7 0 0	0 0 0	7 0 0	0 0 0
4 Technical aspects	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	7 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0
5 Relations	0 0 0	0 0 0	8 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0
6 Cultural change	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	7 0 0	8 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0
7 Networking	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0

Fig. 8

Where:

- The cell with the bolder line (E6) indicates the origin of the Action;
- The numbers in the cells (A1; A2; A3; B3; B5; E3; E6; F4; F6; G1; G3) indicate where we see an effect of the action and how strong this effect appears in each cell;
- On D1 you can see a negative effect happening.

It is quite intuitive to understand that the more cells are involved and the higher the evaluations for each cell, the more a certain action can be considered of impact. Also, the more we have red and orange cells involved the more we are touching the leverage points of our community system increasing the impact of the action.

This kind of reasoning will be performed action by action and then observing the Grid Calculator that presents the sum of the actions to have a general idea of the overall impact of our actions.

GRID PRESENTING THE SUM OF THE 30 ACTIONS:

Actions Categories	Actors Categories								
	U Upper Institutional Levels	A Municipality Political	B Municipality Organization	C Controlled Entities	D Suppliers	E Organizations	F Businesses	G Public	H Networks
	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e
1 Vision	0 0 0	270 0 0	0 0 0	20 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	34 0 0	56 0 0	0 0 0
2 Organization	18 0 0	167 0 0	57 0 0	20 0 0	36 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	16 0 0
3 Planning	0 0 0	91 0 0	15 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	156 0 0	0 0 0	7 0 0	0 0 0
4 Technical aspects	5 0 0	70 0 0	225 0 0	145 0 0	44 0 0	0 0 0	65 0 0	32 0 0	0 0 0
5 Relations	0 0 0	0 0 0	43 0 0	14 0 0	0 0 0	67 0 0	0 0 0	79 0 0	22 0 0
6 Cultural change	34 0 0	21 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	65 0 0	228 0 0	45 0 0	280 0 0	0 0 0
7 Networking	0 0 0	0 0 0	17 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	76 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0

Fig. 8

The image above is just an example of the Grid showing the sum of 30 hypothetical Baseline Actions. You can intuitively spot cells where the values are high and cells where nothing is happening. This is a picture of your community and you’ll learn how to read it with a little practice²², it can tell you much more than it seems at first sight.

The tutor will be trained to analyze the grid and the results coming out of it, for the moment let’s just notice 3 small things to begin with to understand the mechanism. In the grid above we can observe:

	Observations	Meanings/Considerations	To do
1	There are orange cells at zero or very low (U1 ; F3 ; E1 ; G3)	None of our most important actions acts on those leverage	Understand why. Plan to produce impact there (check the MiTS Database).
2	Considerations on pink/red cells: A1 is quite high but B3 is	There is a strong “drive” in the political area, but not much resulting planning going on.	Investigate on why (lack of communication, lack of resources, internal conflicts,

²² We are also planning software and infographics aids based on typical patterns that we can easily recognize and explain. More patterns will emerge with the use of the system within the pioneers and the CoP.

	rather low.	This could strongly prevent concrete effects on the field.	etc.).
3	G6 is high A6 is low.	Is there a strong cultural innovation process going on in civil society which is not reflected in political representation? This can lead to conflict and many other problems.	Carefully verify the situation. Plan/act to restore balance if possible (check the Database).

Fig. 9

The aggregated data will offer you also a few other indicators (see an example below):

1. Cell scores shows the scores broken down by cell type, the original values in orange and red cells are shown multiplied respectively by 2 and 3;
2. Grid total score shows the total score of the grid;
3. The Average Action Efficacy (AAE) shows the percentage of effectiveness of the actions compared to the maximum obtainable score²³.

For all these values a simple statement can be enough for now: the higher the better.

	Baseline			Potential			Evaluation		
Cells scores	6208	2780	1506	0	0	0	0	0	0
Grid total score	10494			0			0		
AAE %	56			0			0		

Fig. 10

So far we are still working on our Baseline, potential and evaluation data are not part of the game yet. These data will take on a much more interesting meaning when we start planning and evaluating the results of our work.

The baseline in practice: baseline qualitative evaluation adding ECs

²³ To calculate this data we are considering the maximum possible score for the grid as 630, as if each cell had the same value, instead of 810 which is the maximum achievable value considering the multiplier effect of orange and red cells (AAE formula is: "Grid_Total_Score: x = 630:100"). This means that the work on the leverage Cells gives a bust in the percentage value we present. If every cell of the grid was set at 10 you would get a 129% indication.

We can see now how to evaluate our action in a more qualitative way. This can be done using the 5 Evaluation Cycles that we saw before. The process is quite simple, make yourself the questions and try to give the best answer available.

Once again, we are not going for “precision” or scientific absoluteness here, we want a general picture good enough to inform the following phases. In the platform you can add your answers to each single action and then view the aggregate result as a percentage of the maximum possible score²⁴ in the table below:

Evaluation Cycles %	HHH			WHO			FLUX			D. ADAPT VALUE			D. ADAPT RES.		
	B	P	E	B	P	E	B	P	E	B	P	E	B	P	E
	456	0	0	345	0	0	120	0	0	50	0	0	45	0	0

Fig. 11

As before: the higher the better.

Let’s start planning

So now we have our baseline and we can move to the next, more exciting phase of planning, designing and moving to action. We do this in two ways:

1. Supporting existing actions
2. Creating new actions

Supporting existing Actions

Practically speaking, having a sort of full picture in front of you will allow you to play with your community system of actions. This is the right time to work on the potential of the actions we put in our grid. This phase could develop quite smoothly and efficiently if the baseline is completed beforehand²⁵.

Review all actions and try to imagine where you could improve the impact or if you could produce impact in cells that are currently not interested by the action.

²⁴ The maximum possible score here is 30 for the single Action and 900 for the set of 30 Actions.

²⁵ Check [Annex 2](#) about the different ways of work planning.

SINGLE ACTION GRID:

		Actors Categories							
Actions Categories	U Upper Institutional Levels	A Municipality Political	B Municipality Organization	C Controlled Entities	D Suppliers	E Organizations	F Businesses	G Public	H Networks
	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e
1 Vision	0 0 0	2 5 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	-2 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	7 7 0	0 0 0
2 Organization	0 0 0	7 7 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0
3 Planning	0 0 0	4 7 0	5 5 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	7 7 0	0 0 0	7 7 0	0 0 0
4 Technical aspects	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	7 3 0	0 0 0	0 0 0
5 Relations	0 0 0	0 0 0	8 8 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0
6 Cultural change	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	7 7 0	8 7 0	0 5 0	0 0 0
7 Networking	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0

Fig. 12

Using the hypothetical action that we have already seen before, the work on the potential may show different situations:

1. Cells where we don't see a way to improve the action because the evaluation is already quite high, like A2, B5, E3, E6, G1, G3. Here we will indicate the same value as the one we used on the Baseline evaluation;
2. Cells where we can see space for improvement like A1, A3, D1, G6;
3. Cells where we imagine a reduction of the impact like F4.

We will do the same with the Evaluation Cycles of the action.

Please consider that very often, the improvement can be obtained by connecting the action with a different one already present in our list or planning a new one. For example, the "Collective food garden" action can be linked to the "Rainwater collection DIY course" making both more effective. You can set connections between actions using a specific linking tool in the platform.

After adding the potential to all the actions we will also have a new picture in the aggregated view, a perfect situation to start the Planning Cycle²⁶:

1. **Spot where “energy” is already operating** - If a successful action²⁷ is spotted in the baseline then there must be a lot of energy there, so you can ask yourself and the actors involved in that particular action a few questions:
 - a. Is there an easy way to support or increase the available “energy” there²⁸?
 - b. Are there other actors that should be involved to support the action?
 - c. Could this action fulfill other functions (produce effects on other/more cells)?
 - d. Is the action already supporting a flux?
 - e. Can we make this action important for Deep Adaptation?
 - f. Can we easily connect this action to other actions in our baseline?
2. **Write a simple plan to do what is needed** to improve the situation if you find good and easy answers to those questions. If not, go to point 3 of this cycle.
3. **Move to another successful action.**

The meaning of this planning cycle is to facilitate you in putting resources (time, people, energy, money) **where there are the best conditions for positive use and results**. When you have good results, then the subsequent planning becomes easier (more energy in place, more will, more commitment, etc).

Create a new Action

In addition to planning on existing actions, you can start planning completely new actions. There are many ways to use your baseline for this, let's see some ideas:

1. You may spot empty cells where nothing is happening (maybe orange or red cells which are clearly important) and you can decide to do something to fill the void.
2. You may spot cells with a lot of activities, which for some reason do not score high after analysing them through the ECs. So you know that there is potential energy there (probably people ready to act, maybe other resources) and you could plan a completely new action to “move” the situation.
3. You may already have projects going on (Covenant of Mayors, EU projects, national projects, etc.) and you can inform the planning of those using information and insights emerging from MiTS.
4. And so on...

To plan a new action you can first check what the MiTS Database offers to help your work on the cells of your interest. You can search the database in different ways, indicating the cell of your

²⁶ This way to plan is strongly inspired and evolved by the insights of David Holmgren's permaculture framework - Permaculture: Principles & Pathways Beyond Sustainability - D. Holmgren's - Holmgren Design Services 2002 - ISBN-13: 978-0646418445

²⁷ High Grid score with many cells involved. High Evaluation Cycles score. High potential.

²⁸ More support, equipment, logistics, specialized people, dissemination, communication, etc.

interest, the actors, topics, etc. What you get is a set of suggested Actions/Tools and all the connections to other related Actions/Tools that might be useful in your situation.

The Tools in the database are designed with the transition principles and the ECs (Evaluation Cycles) in mind. This should lead to common synergic actions (when possible), effectiveness and a good balance between efficiency and resilience.

But the MiTS Database is just at the beginning, so you might not find yet what you are looking for. If you then design an action from scratch that action might later contribute to enrich the database.

Evaluate

Each action implemented should be evaluated in its specific impact in terms of technological, social or institutional change and community resilience (e.g. climate adaptation, equity, cross-community links, etc.), using appropriate indicators. Different evaluation Tools will be available in the **MITS Database**.

A list of useful indicators can either be included in the actions description during the creation of the baseline or be added in a second moment. But for each action you should indicate an evaluation deadline. This may vary substantially depending on the Action. The following table shows some examples:

Action type	Evaluation Deadline
Awareness Rising Show on Climate Change: one night show for children and families.	Immediate Evaluation. Poll and interview immediately after the event.
Green Electricity Switch Contract Campaign	Evaluation after 6 month of activity
Air Quality Monitoring	Periodic Evaluation each year

Table. 6

To run the evaluation we will use the third column in our Grid, like in the example below:

SINGLE ACTION GRID:

		Actors Categories							
Actions Categories	U Upper Institutional Levels	A Municipality Political	B Municipality Organization	C Controlled Entities	D Suppliers	E Organizations	F Businesses	G Public	H Networks
	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e	b p e
1 Vision	0 0 0	2 5 4	0 0 0	0 0 0	-2 0 1	0 0 0	0 0 0	7 7 7	0 0 5
2 Organization	0 0 0	7 7 6	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0
3 Planning	0 0 0	4 7 7	5 5 7	0 0 0	0 0 0	7 7 6	0 0 0	7 7 7	0 0 0
4 Technical aspects	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 8	0 0 0	0 0 0	7 3 1	0 0 0	0 0 0
5 Relations	0 0 0	0 0 0	8 8 8	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0
6 Cultural change	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	7 7 4	8 7 7	0 5 4	0 0 0
7 Networking	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0

Fig. 13

And we can notice that:

1. In A1, A2, E3, E6, F4, G6 the effect is less than the potential we expected;
2. In A3, B5, F6, G1, G3 the effect is aligned with expectations;
3. In B3 and D1 the effect is even more than we expected, notice how in D1 we moved from a negative impact to a slightly positive one (well done);
4. In C4 and H1 we have completely unexpected positive effects.

Suggestion: stating clearly since from an early phase the expected goal of the action, the driver and the tension²⁹ (in the way the S3 suggests), can prove very useful to your evaluation.

Closing circle to a new baseline

The action evaluation closes a circle and the evaluation will become the new *Action Baseline* from which a new circle can start and so on. We could also call this: *Baseline Loop*.

In the next picture you can see the flow of the MiTS activity. There is a starting up phase which then becomes a circular activity that, in theory, could run forever.

²⁹ Here you can find the S3 patterns: "[driver mapping](#)" pattern and "[navigate via tension](#)" pattern

Fig. 14

But MiTS is not forever

Before explaining how to manage the circularity of MiTS it's very important to say that the System is not designed to run forever. The real purpose of MiTS is to become useless³⁰.

The idea is that the more the community uses it the more the local awareness and culture around sustainability should evolve. Attitudes that within the MiTS are now fostered by the use of the Grid, the ECs, the Database etc. should become habits, the normal way to go, a shared culture.

MiTS is not designed to close the community in a cage of rules, but to build familiarity and safety around a new set of principles and methodologies, having the time to fully appreciate all the advantages of a new way.

Ideally, each community that adopts MiTS will get to the point of not needing it anymore, the timing can be very different, but the potential is the typical one of an exponential spread.

The Baseline Loop

The idea is that a community should keep MiTS going as long as it considers it useful. We can imagine different ways to manage the loop of actions but for the pioneer phase we suggest to proceed as follows.

³⁰ There is a strong analogy here with what Harrison Owen says about [Open Space Technology](#), a methodology that is quite familiar and used within the Transition Movement and many other "social innovation" experiments. You can find the entry in the database ([here](#)).

Closed Loop

A starting point with your first BaseLine Evaluation (when you fill the sub-columns in the *Baseline* and *Potential* spaces [b and p respectively] on your Grid) and then you close the cycle deciding a closing date after 1 year (or whatever you think is appropriate) to evaluate the new situation in the sub-columns reserved for *Evaluation* (sub-columns e).

After this, you start a new Loop from a completely empty grid and:

- You may decide to keep some of the actions and the values in the sub-column e of those actions will become the new sub-column b for the new cycle.
- Then you will select a number of new actions to complete the set.

With every new loop you'll be able to compare the general picture and, hopefully, to easily show the improvements also to those not directly involved in the use of the MiTS.

Enrich and populate the Database

Within the Transition movement we have quite a lot of tools that we can consider ready to be loaded into the MiTS Database. We are also collecting materials coming from many other networks and disciplines. It will take a little time and a dedicated team to do this job in a proper way, but we are confident that we can do this (at least in English) in time to provide a basic version of the database to the pioneers.

This will only be the starting point, since the plan is to see the collection of records grow over time with the help of the pilots and other practitioners.

5 - MiTS Adaptation

As we already mentioned we can imagine many ways to change the elements of the MiTS to serve different contexts. But now that you know a little more about it, you can easily understand how deeply a change in a portion of the structure can affect the others.

The most delicate aspect is the relationship between the Grid and the Database. As you know, the records in the database are connected to the cells; therefore, if you move the cells and/or the columns, the records in the database should be updated accordingly.

Therefore for this phase of testing of the MiTS through the Pioneers, we strongly suggest to use everything as it is.

Columns position change

One change we might consider feasible is about the column position. In other words, a change of the relational distance between Actors Categories. This can help the correct visualization of a different structure of your reality and you could do this without changing the identification letter assigned to the column (in this way the references in the database will stay the same).

Columns elimination

We can already imagine situations where column C (Controlled Entities) might not exist. In that case we can imagine a grid without that column without necessarily touching the database structure (the records of the database referring to that column will simply not be used).

ANNEX 1

Working with fluxes

We briefly saw fluxes in 2.4 and we try now to provide some indications about the possibilities we have to generate, interfere and take advantage of them.

Spreading memes

This is a very effective way to create the condition to generate or influence a flux and, very important, it is something we can constantly do while we implement every action.

First of all, what's a meme³¹?

A meme is an idea, behavior, or style that spreads from person to person within a culture—often with the aim of conveying a particular phenomenon, theme, or meaning represented by the meme. A meme acts as a unit for carrying cultural ideas, symbols, or practices, that can be transmitted from one mind to another through writing, speech, gestures, rituals, or other imitable phenomena with a mimicked theme. Supporters of the concept regard memes as cultural analogues to genes in that they self-replicate, mutate, and respond to selective pressures.³²

As the historian Yuval Noah Harari poses it in its book Sapiens:

This approach is sometimes called memetics. It assumes that, just as organic evolution is based on the replication of organic information units called 'genes', so cultural evolution is based on the replication of cultural information units called 'memes'. Successful cultures are those that excel in reproducing their memes, irrespective of the costs and benefits to their human hosts.

There is a set of powerful memes that we can spread around to help our purpose and facilitate the creation of a useful flux that will help our community. Here is a short list of these memes, we could certainly identify many others, but we know those in the list as definitely effective and it is therefore reasonable to start from here:

Useful memes:

Meme		Extended concept
1	Producing energy costs energy.	ERoEI concept , energy return on energy invested. Investing more energy than the amount you can get in return is pointless.

³¹ Quick reference on Wikipedia: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Meme>

³² The meme in popular culture generally is mostly identified with the "Internet meme", which is a concept that spreads rapidly from person to person via the Internet, largely through Internet-based E-mailing, blogs, forums, imageboards like 4chan, social networking sites like Facebook, Instagram, or Twitter, instant messaging, social news sites or thread sites like Reddit, and video hosting services like YouTube and Twitch.

2	Zero impact does not exist.	Every action, every technology has an impact on the local and global system. Zero waste, zero emission and so on are slogans not connected to reality.
3	Free energy does not exist.	Strictly connected to EROEI . Laws of thermodynamics are quite clear here. Harvesting and or producing energy implies use of energy and resources.
4	Free meals do not exist in nature.	Same concept as above. Having different ways to express the meme lets you adapt to the context.
5	The more we become efficient in using resources (or energy) the more resources we use.	Jevons paradox (or rebound effect). Occurs when technological progress or government policy increases the efficiency with which a resource is used (reducing the amount necessary for each single use), but the rate of consumption of that resource rises due to increasing demand.
6	A huge amount of energy is contained in every object of common use.	Embodied energy . We don't use energy only when we switch the light on or we fill the car tank. Every single object embeds in itself all the energy that was used to produce it from the very first step of the production chain.
7	We can no longer burn anything.	Global warming is now so advanced that we should avoid burning anything. We know we must subtract CO ₂ from the atmosphere in all possible ways just to hope to stay under 1.5° C. Burning shouldn't be an option anymore.
8	Climate Emergency.	After decades of inaction on Global Warming, we are now in the Climate Emergency and we need radical decisions to cope with the present situation.
9	We have other ways to practice democracy.	The representative democracy that we know and use in a large part of the developed world is not the only way to go nor the most adequate to solve the big problems we have to face ³³ .
10	We must stop producing waste	This is connected to many of the concepts above, we can't afford to waste energy (6), raw material and the cost of recycling chains (2;3), etc. through the production of all kinds of waste.

³³ This will be explored and practiced within the governance model of MiTS. There are many situations when we can easily decide to replace representative democracy with other methodologies (for example with Deliberative Democracy) and others where we can simply help representative democracy with support methodologies.

The way we spread the memes is extremely important. We must be careful to fulfill the following conditions:

1. These are mostly scientific concepts. They don't belong to a party, a particular political area, a group, a brand, a flag or whatever. Ideally we want them to appear in messages coming from every possible direction. Therefore every time we spot the possibility to introduce one or more of these memes in messages going around our community, no matter what the origin or signature of the message is, we should do it.
2. We don't need to connect the meme with its possible solution, this is not what we are trying to do. Creating the flux is not proposing solutions, it is about creating the space where problems can be analyzed to eventually find solutions.
3. Remember that every action in your baseline is potentially a very good vector for many of these memes. Be focused and include the memes when possible. You have a push for that in the Flux Evaluation Cycle.

Examples 1

We can imagine a municipality producing the instruction guide for the separate waste collection in its territory. Here is a way to introduce a meme in the title:

Title of the guide	Title + memes #10
Recycling the right way to protect your future	Until we manage to <u>stop producing waste</u> recycle to protect your future

As you can see, the original title (on the left column) pushes “recycling” as “the solution” and we know very well that this is not the case³⁴. Recycling is, at best, a good way to keep waste dispersion in the environment under control, but it is energetically and economically very expensive: fundamentally unsustainable except in limited cases.

The real solution is *avoiding the production of waste*. However, it takes time to evolve our production and distribution system to obtain that. Therefore, in the meantime recycling is a transition solution. We can then use a different title for our guide introducing this concept and facilitating the flux toward the real solution.

Examples 2

An environmental association is helping the local government to promote the substitution of old wood stoves, very polluting, with more efficient home heating systems.

Message	Message + memes 2#, #5, #7, #8
Your old stove is no longer legal due to its impact on the environment and health. Take advantage of the economic incentives reserved for those who replace their old stove	Your old stove is no longer legal due to its impact on the environment and health. Because of the global <u>Climatic Emergency</u> and local pollution, we also know that we

³⁴ In case you are not familiar with this concept here is a very quick summary article about plastic on the [Guardian](#), but the same is true for many other materials.

with a modern, efficient and non-polluting system.	<u>should avoid any form of combustion</u> from now on. Take advantage of the economic incentives reserved for those who replace their old stove with a modern, efficient and <u>low-polluting</u> system and <u>try to reduce your need for heat by insulating the rooms.</u>
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Wave riding

Another way to spread the fluxes is the so-called *wave riding*. In our society and media we can clearly observe waves of topics emerging in particular moments and shining under a bright light for weeks or months or even years. We can also call it trends or fashion of the moment or hot news, etc.

You can combine these waves with spreading memes. You just need to spot the wave and add your message taking advantage of the communicative energy the waves bring.

Example 3

At the moment we can observe a big attention devoted to the “plastic problem”. Many may think that this is simply one of the numerous problems we have, but now the focus is there. Therefore, instead of trying to move the focus to something else, take advantage of it and shoot your memes just in front of the crest of the wave.

For instance plan a “plastic free” campaign or activity but use it to spread the memes #2, 6# and #10 stating in you messages concepts like:

We want to make the plastic disappear and with it all the disposable

Every object you use only once represents a waste of energy,
raw materials and produces direct and indirect pollution.

In this way you connect to the “plastic wave”, while at the same time you are introducing something wider, spreading memes to support your Flux.

ANNEX 2

Baseline creation

This is the initial main real task of the Local Implementation Team but for many reasons the group can try to escape this stage with the urgency of DOING PRACTICAL STUFF quickly to feel good, prove they are useful, show how good they are to the external observers, etc. It might prove to be difficult to manage this urgency, therefore, we can consider three ways to go:

1. Basic Baseline
2. Complex Baseline
3. Deferred Baseline

Basic Baseline

Consists in choosing and analysing a set of 30 Actions that are already in place in the community (observed actions). It gives you a picture of what was happening before the introduction of MiT. After this, the LIT will perform the potential speculations, plan and/or support new Actions, etc. This, in theory, should be the cleaner way to go, but it might prove too slow for the LIT or not interesting enough (too mechanical to keep the commitment at a high level). It has the advantage to be very similar to other well known processes like, for instance, the Covenant of Mayors, making it somehow “familiar” to municipalities’ people.

If you decide with the LIT to stick to this kind of planning, we warn you to resist the temptation to think about future or potential actions while performing the Baseline analysis. In case you need to experiment with something different to keep the LIT energy high, we suggest you to look at the other two Baseline planning cycles.

Complex Baseline

In adopting this strategy, we can let the LIT mix existing Actions with those under design. This is messier and creates several complexities in the reading of the Baseline initial picture and in the future evaluation (you are basically mixing an evaluation and a potential - not good under the research point of view), but can be a way to go to keep the LIT energetic and really involved (I think we must be activists first and researchers later). There are risks connected:

1. Lower systemic vision effect (risk of mixing reality with speculation);
2. Lower impact of the before/after comparison on the Grid Calculator;
3. New actions not designed under the MiT methodology (the tutor must be careful);
4. Never get to a real baseline to start from and compare to later on.

All this is manageable but requires a higher commitment and attention from the tutor.

Deferred Baseline

Using this approach the baseline is created adding new and observed actions on-the-go one at a time for a period of time. This way is emerging from the work of the first pioneer (Valsamoggia, Italy) where we can see a quite coordinated flow of activity in real time management of emergent opportunities and reactions to problems. This way is not particularly desirable in a project with a limited time to observe the process (like this one) but probably more realistic for a real life everyday use of the MiT. Proceeding this way you will observe a full picture only after a few months, six or so, and from there you will start to improve or support the actions. There are advantage though:

1. It seems a more progressive way to go and learn for the LIT. You probably have people already very busy and this way creates space and time for them to be present with quality time.
2. It fits very well with the use of th S3 because it's easier to involve the right people in each analysis and decision process due the greater availability of time to do so.
3. It feels less an "experiment" and more an operational tool.

You may consider to go this way if you have a very organic LIT deeply influencing the municipality activity and the actions within the community.

END OF DOCUMENT